

THE EFFECT OF WORK DISCIPLINE, COMPETENCE, AND REWARDS ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AT BANK BCA KFPT BATAM

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of Work Discipline, Competence, and Reward on Employee Performance at Bank BCA KFPT Batam. This research employs a quantitative method with an associative approach. The population consisted of 198 employees, and the sample was determined using the Slovin formula with a 10% margin of error, resulting in 66 respondents. The sampling technique used was Simple Random Sampling. Data analysis was conducted using multiple linear regression with the assistance of SPSS software. The validity test results indicated that all questionnaire items were valid, with r-count values greater than 0.244 and significance values less than 0.05. The reliability test showed that all variables were reliable, with Cronbach's Alpha values greater than 0.60 (Work Discipline = 0.876; Competence = 0.859; Reward = 0.827; Employee Performance = 0.873). The classical assumption tests demonstrated that the data were normally distributed (Sig. 0.078 > 0.05), with no multicollinearity (Tolerance > 0.10 and VIF < 10) and no heteroscedasticity. Simultaneously, Work Discipline, Competence, and Reward had a significant effect on Employee Performance, with an F-value of 29.703 > 2.75 and a significance level of 0.000 < 0.05. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was 0.590, indicating that 59.0% of the variation in Employee Performance could be explained by the three independent variables, while the remaining 41.0% was influenced by other factors not examined in this study.

Keywords: *Work Discipline, Competence, Reward, Employee Performance.*

INTRODUCTION

Besides discipline, employee competency also significantly impacts performance. Competence reflects an individual's ability to perform work based on their knowledge, skills, and work attitude. In the banking sector, which is full of challenges, digital technology developments, and intense competition, employees are required to continuously improve their competencies to provide optimal service to customers. Competent employees not only understand their core duties and functions but are also able to adapt to constantly evolving banking systems and policies. These include salaries, bonuses, allowances, promotions, and non-financial recognition such as praise and certificates of achievement. A good and fair reward system will foster satisfaction, loyalty, and high morale among employees. Conversely, unfair or inadequate rewards can lead to dissatisfaction and decreased work motivation, ultimately leading to decreased performance. The performance of BCA Bank KFPT Batam employees is one of the factors determining the quality of banking services in the Batam region. In practice, several issues related to employee discipline and productivity persist, such as delays in completing administrative tasks, a lack of initiative in customer service, and suboptimal attendance. Furthermore, employee competency in information technology and digital banking needs to be continuously improved to enable them to adapt to the innovations in digital-based financial services that are a primary demand of modern banking.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance (Y) Employee performance is a crucial element in determining an organization's success in achieving its goals. In the modern workplace, performance is viewed not only as the end result of a person's

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work but also encompasses the processes and behaviors demonstrated during the execution of tasks. High-performing employees are those who demonstrate competence, responsibility, discipline, and dedication in completing their work according to established standards and within specified timeframes. According to Mangkunegara (2021), performance is the work results, both qualitatively and quantitatively, achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with their assigned responsibilities. Performance can be measured by how effectively and efficiently an individual carries out their assigned work. In an organizational context, employee performance reflects not only individual achievement but also the overall productivity of the organization.

Work Discipline (X_1) Work discipline is a fundamental aspect of human resource management, playing a crucial role in creating order, accountability, and effective task execution within an organization. Discipline not only refers to adherence to applicable regulations and procedures, but also reflects an individual's awareness of voluntarily fulfilling obligations to achieve shared goals. According to Hasibuan (2021), work discipline is an individual's awareness and willingness to comply with all company regulations and applicable social norms. Discipline is a key factor in developing a professional and responsible work character in employees. Employees with high levels of discipline tend to work according to standards, maintain time, and adhere to all organizational policies without excessive supervision. Sedarmayanti (2022) stated that work discipline is a tool for organizations to motivate employees to work effectively and efficiently in accordance with established regulations. Good discipline indicates an employee's awareness of their responsibilities, while poor discipline reflects weak compliance and commitment to the job.

Competence (X_2) Competence is a fundamental element that describes an individual's ability to perform work in accordance with job requirements and organizational standards. Competence encompasses a combination of knowledge, skills, and attitudes demonstrated in the performance of daily tasks.

According to Wibowo (2020), competence is an individual's ability to perform a job or task based on skills and knowledge, supported by a work attitude that aligns with job requirements. Competence indicates the extent to which an employee has the ability to achieve the performance expected by the organization. Sedarmayanti (2022) states that competence reflects an individual's capacity to demonstrate superior work performance in real-world situations. Competence extends beyond technical mastery to encompass behavioral values, social skills, and an understanding of organizational culture. Therefore, competence is a crucial indicator in determining employee effectiveness and professionalism.

Hypothesis A hypothesis is a temporary answer to a research problem whose truth still needs to be empirically proven through data analysis. Based on the framework above, this research hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

1. There is a significant influence between Work Discipline (X_1) on Employee Performance (Y) at Bank BCA KFPT Batam.
2. There is a significant influence between Competence (X_2) and Employee Performance (Y) at Bank BCA KFPT Batam.
3. There is a significant influence between Awards (X_3) on Employee Performance (Y) at Bank BCA KFPT Batam.
4. There is a significant simultaneous influence between Work Discipline (X_1), Competence (X_2), and Rewards (X_3) on Employee Performance (Y) at Bank BCA KFPT Batam.
- 5.

METHOD

Population According to Kuncoro (2020:103), a population is a complete group of elements, usually people, objects, transactions, or events that we are interested in studying or that become the object of research. The population in this study is all employees of Bank BCA KFPT Batam, totaling 1,000.198 Employees .

Sample According to Sugiyono (2021:126), a sample is part of the number and characteristics of a population used to obtain research data. If the population is too large, researchers can take a portion of the population that is considered to represent the whole by using a particular sampling technique. In this study, the sampling technique uses the Slovin formula (Umar, 2020:179) to determine the number of samples with an error rate (e) of 10%, because the population is classified as moderate and homogeneous. Sampling is based on Solvin's opinion with the formula (Umar, 2020:179)

$$n = \frac{N}{N(e)2 + 1}$$

Information :

n = sample size N = population size

e = Percentage of allowance for inaccuracy due to errors of 10% (umar, 2020: 146).

The coefficient of determination (R²) aims to determine the extent to which the independent variable can explain the dependent variable. This study uses the Adjusted R Square model because there are more than two variables. The Adjusted R Square formula is:

$$R_{adj}^2 = 1 - \left[\frac{(1 - R^2)(n - 1)}{n - k - 1} \right]$$

Where N is the number of observations and p is the number of parameters of the coefficient of determination.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bank Central Asia (BCA) is one of the largest national private banks in Indonesia, founded in 1957 under the initial name Bank Central Asia NV. Since its inception, BCA has been committed to being a trusted, professional, and customer-focused financial institution. In line with developments in the banking sector and the national economy, BCA continues to demonstrate significant growth through improved services, strengthened information technology, and expanded office networks throughout Indonesia. As part of this service expansion, Bank BCA established the Batam Functional Transaction Service Office (KFPT) to serve customers in the Batam area of the Riau Islands. This office plays a crucial role as an operational unit supporting various financial transactions, such as account opening, cash deposits, withdrawals, transfers, payments, and other digital banking products and services. Bank BCA KFPT Batam is committed to creating a productive and conducive work environment through the implementation of work discipline, employee competency development, and the provision of rewards to high-performing employees. These efforts ensure that each employee is motivated and performs optimally in providing the best service to customers. The sampling technique used was Simple Random Sampling, a random sampling technique in which every individual in the population has an equal chance of being selected as a respondent. This aims to obtain objective data that is representative of the entire population. This research was conducted using a closed-ended questionnaire distributed to employees of Bank BCA KFPT Batam. The questionnaire contained statements related to the research variables: work discipline, competence, rewards, and employee performance. The normality test can be displayed using a histogram, as shown in the image below. The histogram resembles an inverted bell that fills the bell line, indicating that the data is normally distributed.

Histogram Graph of Normality Test

In the image below, you can see the PP Plot normality graph. It can be seen that the points are spread around the diagonal line and the distribution . Multiple linear regression is used to predict the effect of independent variables on

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the dependent variable to prove whether or not there is a functional relationship between these variables. The regression equation can be found in the SPSS output in the coefficient table. Multiple regression analysis is an analysis used by researchers who intend to predict the condition (rise or fall) of an independent variable, if two or more independent variables as predictor factors are manipulated (their value is increased or decreased). The multiple regression model of Work Discipline, Competence and Rewards that influence the performance of BCA KFPT Batam Bank employees is as follows.

Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3,837	4,262		.900	.371
1 Work Discipline	-.037	.190	-.038	-.195	.846
Competence	.360	.166	.365	2,168	.034
Award	.564	.182	.483	3,092	.003

The constant of 3.837 shows that if the variables Work Discipline, Competence, and Rewards are considered constant (with a value of zero), then Employee Performance is 3.837. Thus, it can be concluded that of the three independent variables studied, only Competence and Rewards have a significant influence on the Performance of BCA KFPT Batam Bank Employees, while Work Discipline does not have a significant influence.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the data analysis above using IBM SPSS software, in relation to the Problem Formulation and Research Objectives in Chapter I, and also in proving the Hypothesis in Chapter II, the author has reached the following conclusions:

1. The Work Discipline variable (X1) apparently does not have a significant effect on Employee Performance (Y) at Bank BCA KFPT Batam. From the analysis results, the t-value of Work Discipline is -0.195 with a significance value of 0.846 > 0.05. The regression results show a coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.475. This means that 47.5% of the dependent variable, namely Employee Performance, has a significant effect on employee performance.
2. The Competence variable (X2) has a significant effect on Employee Performance (Y) at Bank BCA KFPT Batam. From the analysis results, it is known that the t-value of the Competence variable is 2.168 with a significance value of 0.034 < 0.05. The regression results show a coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.507. This means that 50.7% of the dependent variable, namely Employee Performance, can be explained by the Competence variable, while 49.3% is influenced by other factors.
3. The Reward variable (X3) has a significant effect on Employee Performance (Y) at Bank BCA KFPT Batam. From the analysis results, it is known that the t-value of the Reward variable is 3.092 with a significance value of 0.003 < 0.05. The regression results show a coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.544. This means that 54.4% of the dependent variable, namely Employee Performance, can be explained by the Reward variable, while 45.6% is influenced by other factors. This variable is the most dominant variable.

SUGGESTION

The suggestions that the author needs to convey to Bank BCA KFPT Batam are as follows:

1. Although Work Discipline does not have a significant effect in this study, management still needs to maintain and improve employee discipline through consistent supervision and the implementation of clear work rules so that performance stability is maintained.
2. Employee competency has been proven to have a significant impact on performance. Therefore, management needs to improve training programs, skills development, and professional development on an ongoing basis to improve the technical and non-technical abilities of employees.
3. Overall, the management of Bank BCA KFPT Batam needs to integrate strategies for improving work discipline, developing competencies and providing rewards simultaneously so that employee performance can improve optimally and sustainably.

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